

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #6

Urban Sustainability:

Green Materials and Recycling in Construction

By University of Sassari

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Executive Summary

Figure 25. – Promoting Sustainability in Urban Areas through the Use of Green Materials and Recycling in Building Construction - Graphical Abstract

Focusing on the building sector, this case study analysed the renovation potential of a complex of abandoned urban industrial buildings in Sassari, Italy, considering embodied energy and carbon related to existing materials and their potential recovery. The results reveal a substantial material recovery

potential, ranging from 25%-35% to 65%-75%. In addition, the type of insulation material used showed a relevant impact on embodied energy and carbon recovery rates, with cork having the potential to reduce overall embodied energy and carbon, Figure 25

Abstract

The European economy relies heavily on the consumption of non-renewable resources such as minerals, metals, concrete and wood, as well as fossil fuels and land to meet the demands of its citizens. As a result, a significant amount of waste is generated, with an average of six tons of waste per person annually. Currently, 51.5% of this waste is disposed of, with only 43.6% being recycled. With Europe importing a large quantity of raw materials, there is a growing need to optimise the use and management of waste materials.

In this context, the building construction sector can play an important role in reducing the raw materials demand by implementing the reclamation, reuse and recycling approach on the huge quantity of stock material typically abandoned along the building lifetime. This is particularly relevant considering the large number of abandoned buildings or buildings which require refurbishing and energy retrofitting in Europe. The implementation of rational and efficient design and construction policies and

practices aimed at supporting the recycling and reuse of building construction waste – including the use of abandoned buildings as materials quarry – and the adoption of green construction practices, based on green materials and renewable energy, can lead to a number of benefits, such as the reduction of raw material extraction, transportation and processing, energy and carbon emission savings, a reduced volume disposal in landfills, and the potential of reducing costs and increase health and life quality in the affected urban areas.

Generally, recycling in the building construction sector specifically involves the collection, processing, and reuse of materials from building construction and demolition sites. Common practices include recycling concrete and asphalt for use in new building projects, using reclaimed wood for flooring and other building components, recycling metals such as steel and copper, the adoption of sustainable and

environmental-friendly materials for building elements, such as insulation, flooring, panelling, etc. However, the potential for reusing a large amount of abandoned material in the building process requires a comprehensive life-cycle approach that encompasses everything from the selection of the construction site to the selection of building materials and design elements, from the construction to its operating life and decommissioning. The present case study explores several methodologies and strategies for recycling and reuse of raw materials in the construction sector, with reference to several existing buildings/urban areas in Sardinia (Italy).

Introduction

A growing recognition of the environmental, economic, and social benefits of sustainable construction practices has led to implementing policies for the recovery and reuse of existing buildings. Nowadays, there is an even greater emphasis on the environmental impact of the construction sector and a growing recognition that material recovery of existing buildings is essential for

maximising sustainability (Yang et al., 2022).

By reusing materials that already exist in the built environment, we can reduce the environmental impact of new construction and minimize material waste. This is particularly important given the finite nature of many of the resources used in construction, such as minerals, metals, and wood. Furthermore, the recovery and reuse of existing buildings may also lead to economic savings (Kylili & Fokaides, 2017), due to the reduction of new materials needed for new construction, and social benefits - such as preservation of historical structures and local architectural character, as well as to revitalise communities and neighbourhoods (Iacovidou & Purnell, 2016).

Various possible degrees of intervention can be employed when it comes to working with existing buildings, and each requires a unique set of skills and knowledge. These

intervention can become increasingly complex and intertwined with environmental concerns, requiring not only an understanding of the immaterial connections between people and place but also of the physical and bioclimatic properties of the building envelope.

Additionally, knowledge of the adaptability of existing structures to new uses is crucial to ensure that they can continue to serve as functional and valuable components of the built environment. According to a residual performance-based approach for technical elements and components (Monsù Scolaro & De Medici, 2021), to minimise material flow and waste creation, a refurbishment intervention should ideally be carried out by conserving and reusing as much material as possible while also minimising the addition of new material. At the same time, the technical design choices should be compatible (from a physical-chemical and mechanical standpoint) with the existing

material and meet the criteria of disassembly, ease of maintenance, and recoverability of the materials and construction solutions adopted, preferably using dry construction technologies where possible.

Over the last decade, life cycle analysis has raised a lot of interest among the research community since it allows to evaluate the environmental impact of a product or service throughout its life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. In the building sector, LCA can provide valuable information about the environmental impact of different retrofitting solutions and material reuse options (Chau et al., 2015), including potential savings from the energy and carbon emission points of view (Schwartz et al., 2018). In addition, the concept of embodied energy and embodied carbon has been introduced to quantify the energy consumption and carbon emissions associated with the entire life cycle of a building material, from extraction and processing to

transportation and installation. Evaluating both the energy and carbon life cycle enables a comprehensive assessment of the material and system performance in terms of primary energy and carbon savings (De Rosa & Bianco, 2023).

This approach enables the optimisation of insulation layer design, such as thickness, based on energy and carbon payback (Azari & Abbasabadi, 2018). Numerous authors have successfully tested this methodology in the building construction and renovation industry. For example, (Braulio-Gonzalo & Bovea (2017) studied the environmental and cost performance of insulation strategies for building envelopes by conducting a life-cycle assessment of the insulation materials. Roberts et al. (2020) investigated the sustainability of building components in terms of life-cycle carbon emissions and developed a trade-off methodology for decision-making purposes. Similarly, Abd Alla et al. (2020)

examined the impact of embodied energy and carbon on energy efficiency measures in the building sector, highlighting the significance of a full life-cycle analysis in determining the performance of insulation layer deployment.

Generally, to adopt a comprehensive and sustainable approach to building retrofitting that promotes material reuse and recycling to optimise refurbishing costs, embodied energy and carbon, the underlying methodology should include several phases (Figure 26):

- **Phase 1:** preliminary assessment of the existing building's end uses, architectural configuration, existing material and structures, and potential retrofitting solutions. The assessment will consider the building's current condition, its history, and its potential for adaptive reuse. The evaluation will

also identify the most promising retrofitting solutions that consider the building's environmental impact, energy efficiency, and the well-being of its occupants.

- **Phase 2:** a preliminary control and verification of material flows of the retrofitting solutions, by analysing the architectural constraints and determining the potential for preserving the existing material and structures, as well as identifying opportunities for material reuse, recycling, and disposal. This involves conducting a preliminary control and verification of material flows during the construction phase.
- **Phase 3:** assessment of technological performance of both existing and new materials, as well as analysing their embodied energy and embodied carbon to evaluate the potential impact of

retrofitting solutions and identify opportunities for energy and carbon savings. In addition, the phase considers factors related to well-being and safety to ensure that the retrofitting design not only improves the building's energy efficiency but also creates a healthier and safer environment for its occupants.

- **Phase 4:** optimization of the retrofitting solutions designed to reduce waste and costs, promote the use of sustainable materials with low embodied energy and low embodied carbon, as well as the requalification and integration of the building in its local context. This phase aims to achieve the best possible balance between environmental, economic, and social sustainability, and to identify and evaluate the potential benefits of each design option. It also involves ensuring the compliance of the retrofitting solutions with all applicable regulations and standards, as well as

the proper coordination with stakeholders and contractors involved in the project.

Figure 26. Building retrofitting design promoting material reuse and recycling.

1	Preliminary assessment	2	Material flow assessment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building end-use • Architectural configuration • Existing materials • Design solutions 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architectural constraints • Material preservation • Demolition • Reuse, recycling and disposal
3	Impact assessment	4	Design optimisation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological performance • Embodied energy • Environmental impact • Well-being 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste and cost reduction • Energy/carbon impact minimisation • Local context integration • Regulation compliance

In this context, the present case study outlines the potential renovation of a former urban industrial area located in Sassari (Sardinia, Italy). The area, inserted in the urban context of the city close to the city centre and well connected with the main road and rail junctions, has been abandoned since the early '80s and is in an advanced state of decay. Starting from the assessment of the current condition of the different buildings located in

the complex, aimed at analysing the different structures, the constituent materials, their condition and remaining performance, and the potential material flows are identified. Then, the potential reuse and recycling of the existing material and new material components are assessed and evaluated in terms of embodied energy, embodied carbon and costs. Different solutions are analysed to determine the optimal material flow configurations to minimise the raw material consumption.

Description of Case Study

The case study relates to a redevelopment and reuse intervention of the "Ex Conceria Costa", an industrial complex located in the urban area of Sassari in Sardinia, Italy (Figure 27).

The building complex was built starting from 1859 and expanded over several decades, which represents an interesting example of

industrial archaeology in Sardinia (Italy). The building was used for leather processing until the early 1950s, then rented as a furniture factory, and eventually abandoned in 1982 due to a fire that made it unusable. The current complex floor plan is due to the numerous changes of use from 1859 to 1936. The first expansion phase involved adding some volumes to the first three factory buildings for the installation of powerful steam engines. Subsequently, two more factory buildings were added, which configured two new internal courtyards (originally used as a city fruit and vegetable market). The main building was built in 1899 and gave the entire complex a stately and imposing appearance: the expansion process, at least until 1910, was based on a unitary project whose floor plan articulation was influenced by the nearby railway, built in 1872. The last growth phase of the complex coincides with the addition of the last internal courtyard in which the power plant for the production of electricity for the building was located.

Figure 27. Location of the case study

Currently, the building complex is abandoned, and the remaining structural components are in an advanced state of decay. Being located near both road and rail junctions, easily accessible on foot or by car, and thanks to its proximity with Sassari's city centre (Figure 26-27), the area has a high potential for

redevelopment and renewal. Its strategic location and accessibility, together with the large courtyard area available and a certain flexibility in the use of spaces, make it an ideal location for a variety of new uses, such as commercial or residential spaces, cultural centres, or educational institutions.

Figure 28. Case study features and its integration in the urban district (Costa, 2013)

The main complex consists of a 3 floor building with about 1543 m² per floor and it was constructed with load-bearing masonry in squared blocks of local limestone, double T steel beam floors, and brick vaults supported by cast iron columns. The external and

internal walls are about 98.33 m³ and 73.83 m³, while the roofs (where still in place) are gabled or hipped and are supported by a structure consisting of wooden trusses, crosspieces, and battens (Figure 29, Figure 29).

Figure 29. Construction details of the main building complex (Costa, 2013)

Case Study

Solution

The experimental methodology proposed in this study is founded on the interdependence between building process and spatial features of a structure. It is based on the notion that the way a building is constructed shapes its spatiality, and vice versa. In this particular case, the methodology explores the idea of a symbiotic relationship between the building process and spatiality, emphasizing the crucial role of reuse, recycling, super-use, and other connected practices. The goal is to investigate a unique concept of "spatiality of recycling," which highlights the potential of repurposing existing materials and spaces in a building. By focusing on recycling and repurposing, this methodology aims to create sustainable solutions for requalification and reuse of existing buildings by recovering materials and their embodied energy and carbon

content. Since the building can be reused in its entirety or in parts, with consideration given to its spatial quality, the spatial and technological quality of certain construction elements, or the quality of the materials, the adopted procedure can be divided into three main phases (Scolaro, 2018):

- **Building structural and material assessment:** the evaluation of the building's planimetric and spatial configuration is carried out to identify the main architectonic and structural features, which allows to identify refurbishment strategies and the consequent modifications required, such as demolition and preservation.
- **Refurbishment strategy:** the constituent materials are broken down and analysed in relation to their technological characteristics, conservation status and residual performance. This allows to evaluate the material flows which can be recovered,

reused and recycled during the refurbishment process.

- **Refurbishment optimisation:** this phase assesses costs, embodied energy and carbon contents of the identified material flows in order to detect the optimal refurbishment strategies to minimise new material consumption and related carbon emissions.

Embodied energy and carbon

The redevelopment of a building depends on its state of decay and may require technically replacement interventions or reuse and implementation of existing building components. Embodied energy can therefore split into three main components (Dixit et al., 2010):

- **Initial embodied energy:** accounting for 75-80% of the total embodied energy of a material, it accounts from the primary energy consumed for the extraction of the raw materials, their processing and transportation and the energy used during the construction phase.

- **Recurring energy:** it refers to energy consumed during the recurrent maintenance of the building as well as any subsequent retrofitting.
- **Disposal embodied energy:** it includes the energy consumption due to demolition and final disposal of the building material.

Therefore, the quantification of the embodied energy is a complex task which adopts a cradle-to-gate approach. In the present work, the Inventory of Energy and Carbon (ICEN) (Dixit et al., 2010) was used to estimate the values of the initial embodied energy of the building constituent materials of the case study under analysis. The ICEN (Inventory of Carbon and Energy) contains average embodied energy data for 30 main categories of materials, referring to the cradle-to-gate phase, from the extraction of raw materials to their transformation and transport

to the construction site. Minimum and maximum EE values are provided in accordance with the literature referenced in the inventory, which takes into account

specific operating conditions that could affect the variations in the EE value of each individual material on a case-by-case basis. The data are shown in the following table.

Table 9. Construction details of the main building complex (Costa, 2013)

	Material	Function	Density (kg/m ³)	Dimension (cm)	Embodied energy (MJ/kg)
Wooden truss	Wood	Structural	640	20 x 20	378.9
Secondary structure	Wood	Structural/Support	640	12 x 12	68.2
Wooden board	Wood	Support	640	3	142.8
Wooden strips	Wood	Support	640	2 x 2	39.8
Roof tiles	Terracotta clay	Finishing	1500	45 x 14	354.8
Masonry blocks	Masonry	Structural	2000	62	1426.0
Plaster	Lime	Finishing	1500	3	52.2

Starting from the values of embodied energy shown in Error! Reference source not found., given the total mass of the construction material I ($m_{i,tot}$) in the building complex, its embodied energy is:

$$EE_{i,tot} = m_{i,tot} \cdot EE_i$$

Since not all the material can be effectively reused or recycled during the refurbishment phase, the recovered embodied energy for material is:

$$EE_{i,R} = m_{i,R} \cdot EE_i = (m_{i,rcy} + m_{i,reu}) \cdot EE_i$$

where $m_{i,rcy}$ and m_{reu} are respectively, the total mass of material i recycled in the production process of other components and the reused total mass (i.e., not demolished).

The ratio between the total embodied energy $EE_{i,tot}$ and the recovered embodied energy $EE_{i,R}$ of material i is called “EE recovering efficiency”:

$$\eta_{R,i} = \frac{EE_{i,R}}{EE_{i,tot}}$$

Generally, the value of the EE recovering efficiency depends on the status of the existing materials in terms of residual technical performance - which can be of various nature depending on the original purpose of the building component (e.g., structural, energy efficiency, hygrometric performance, acoustic insulation, etc.) – on health and safety constraints, the specific refurbishing project under development and on the costs associated with recycling and reuse phases. Following the identification of the initial embodied energy and its potential recovering, the total initial embodied energy of all building components is defined as:

$$EE_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^N m_{i,tot} \cdot EE_i$$

Similarly, the total embodied energy recovered is given by:

$$EE_{tot,R} = \sum_{i=1}^N m_{i,R} \cdot EE_{i,R}$$

and the overall EE and EC recovery indexes are:

$$\eta_{EE} = \frac{EE_{tot,R}}{EE_{tot}}$$

The calculation of the embodied carbon emission related to the production process of each existing component requires knowledge of the energy flows used in the production process, which ideally should be obtained from a detailed case study on the life cycle carbon emission (You et al., 2011). However, due to the complexity and variety of materials, together with the lack of information and data for all countries and materials, retrieving this information could be challenging, and overall because pre-existing old materials and building components impede precisely calculate the environmental impacts associated with the former production processes To tackle this challenge, a simplified approach was presented in De Rosa & Bianco (2023) where the authors used the energy fuel mix of the material or component production country.

Knowing the embodied energy of the material i , its embodied carbon emission is:

$$EC_i = \zeta \cdot EE_i$$

where ζ is the average carbon intensity of the considered country (i.e., Italy) which is determined based on the country's average fuel mix of the industry sector. Based on the authors' work De Rosa & Bianco (2023), the present analysis assumes a constant carbon intensity of 107.3 kgCO₂/MWh for Italy.

Scenario analysis

Recovering existing materials in the construction site for its refurbishing allows the reduction of the consumption of new materials. In order to analyse the potential impact of material recovering for the case study described before, a baseline scenario (BS), which consists of the demolition of the entire building complex and its reconstruction without any recycling or reuse of existing material was defined. Starting from the baseline case, two different scenarios were identified:

- Low recovering scenario (LR): the building structures with a high residual technological performance are reused (i.e., vertical walls), while the others are demolished and disposed. The refurbishment of the unrecovered part is made by using new materials and components.

- High recovering scenario (HR): the buildings are refurbished by keeping all structures with a good residual technological performance, while the others are dismantled and recycled where feasible.

Table 10 and 11 outlines the main assumptions of the two scenarios highlighting the structural elements reuse, which refers to the components which are conserved and refurbished, and demolitions. Since part of the raw materials obtained by the dismantling of the existing structures can be recycled to reduce the amount of new raw materials required for the building complex refurbishment, the tables also report the share of materials recycled and disposed in landfills.

Table 10. Description of the Low Recovery Scenario (LR) assumptions

Building elements	Structural element reuse	Dismantling	
		Material recycling	Landfill disposal
External walls	~25% of the external walls are conserved. The remaining walls are demolished and reconstructed.	~30% of the raw material from the demolished walls is processed and reused onsite.	The unused or recycled materials are processed and disposed in landfill.
Internal wall	~20% of the internal walls are conserved. The remaining walls are demolished and reconstructed.	~30% of the raw materials from the demolished walls is processed and reused onsite.	The unused or recycled materials are processed and disposed in landfill.
Basement and floors	No structural elements are recovered and reused.	~30% of the material is processed and reused onsite.	~70% of the material is transported offsite and disposed in landfills.
Roof	No structural elements are recovered and reused.	~30% of the material is processed and reused onsite.	~70% of the material is transported offsite and disposed in landfills.
External walls	~50% of the external walls are conserved. The remaining walls are demolished and reconstructed.	~50% of the raw material from the demolished walls is processed and reused onsite.	The unused or recycled materials are processed and disposed in landfill.

Building elements	Structural element reuse	Dismantling	
		Material recycling	Landfill disposal
Internal walls	~50% of the internal walls are conserved. The remaining walls are demolished and reconstructed.	~50% of the raw materials from the demolished walls is processed and reused onsite.	The unused or recycled materials are processed and disposed in landfill.
Basemen and floors	~25% of basements and floors are conserved. The remaining walls are demolished and reconstructed.	~50% of the material is processed and reused onsite.	The unused or recycled materials are processed and disposed in landfill.
Roof	No structural elements are recovered and reused.	~50% of the material is processed and reused onsite.	~50% of the material is transported offsite and disposed in landfills.

All considered scenarios aims to fully refurbish the building complex in line with the energy efficiency regulation in place. To this purpose, insulation layers are installed in all scenarios where relevant, and different insulation materials are considered – namely, EPS,

Rockwool and cork. Thermo-physical properties, embodied energy and carbon of the insulation materials, Table 12, are taken into account in the calculation (Hammond & Jones, 2008).

Table 12. Insulation materials data

Insulation material	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Embodied energy (MJ/kg)	Embodied carbon (kgCO ₂ /kg)
Rockwool	92	0.047	16.80	0.501
EPS	16	0.036	88.60	2.641
Cork	180	0.041	4.00	0.119

The LR and HR scenarios are then compared with the baseline scenarios (BS) in order to evaluate the potential impact on embodied energy and carbon on different shares of recovered materials.

Results and Discussion

Based on the structure surveys outlined in the previous section (see Table 12) the assessment of the existing materials was carried out in order to determine the current embodied energy and carbon emissions of the pilot site. Table 13 reports the results of the analysis grouped based on the building structures still in place.

Despite the poor conservation status of most of the building elements, a total embodied energy and carbons of about 938 MWh and 226 tonCO₂eq was computed for the pilot site, with the largest share accounted for basements and floors, followed by external walls. On the other hand, the embodied energy and carbons of the roof elements showed the lowest share, mainly due to the fact that part of the roof structure has been destroyed and/or demolished for safety reason.

Table 13. Available materials, embodied energy and carbon for different structural element

Structures	Volume (m3)	Mass (ton)	Embodied energy (MWh)	Embodied carbon (tonCO2eq)
External walls	295.0	590	159.3	38.2
Internal walls	222.6	443	104.7	25.1
Basements and floors	1234.4	2469	582.9	139.9
Roof	-	109	91.8	23.4

The next stage of the analysis involved the definition of the baseline scenario (BS) which consists of the demolition of the entire building complex and its reconstruction without any recycling or reuse of existing material, which is then processed and disposed in landfills. First, the impact of the dismantling/demolition and disposal process in terms of embodied energy and carbon has been estimated, based on the procedure suggested by Wang et al.

(2018). Considering the processes of demolition, collection and sorting, residual transports and landfill disposal, a total of 513 MWh of primary energy consumption and 54.9 tonCO2eq of carbon emissions are expected (Table 14). This energy and carbon “costs” are then taken into account in the definition of the baseline scenario and added to the overall energy/carbon assessment for the subsequent analysis.

Table 14. Primary energy and carbon emissions related to a full demolition and disposal of the building structures of the case study

Phases	Embodied energy (MWh)	Embodied carbon (tonCO ₂ eq)
Demolition	170	18.2
Collection and sorting	292	31.3
Transport and disposal	51	5.5
Total	513	54.9

The next step involved the definition of the structures of external and internal walls, basements, floors and roof for the new building complex. To maintain consistency, it was assumed to keep the same layout of the complex, but new materials were considered for the structural elements (i.e., vertical walls, basements and floors). Moreover, thermal insulation layers with a thickness of 15 cm were added where relevant to meet the current energy efficiency regulation in

The different insulation materials outlined in Table 9 were considered separately to investigate their influence on energy and carbon emissions. The new structure layouts are:

- **Vertical walls:** structure made of a layer of 38 cm made of bricks and 15 cm thermal insulation added at the external side (for external walls only). A 2-cm finish later made by plaster was also considered.

- **Floors and basements:** concrete slab with structural I-beam and steel joints with a total thickness of 25 cm and finishing layers with plaster and/or tiles based on the specific application. Thermal insulation was also added in the basement where relevant.
- Finally, the roof was assumed to be replaced entirely while keeping the same structural layout and materials, as shown in Figure 29.

Table 15 reports the result of the new embodied energy and carbon obtained for the baseline scenario for each different building element and insulation material used. It can be observed that the horizontal floors accounts for the largest share of embodied energy and carbon, followed by the external walls, basement and internal walls, while the roof is the building element with the lowest impact on energy consumption and carbon emissions.

Table 15. Embodied energy and carbon of the new building in the baseline scenario

Elements	Total surface (m2)	Embodied energy (MWh)		Embodied carbon (tonCO2eq)	
		Material	Value	Material	Value
Internal walls	1108		449		113
External walls	1475	Rockwool	692	Rockwool	161
		EPS	684	EPS	160
		Cork	642	Cork	155

Internal walls	3086	1157		290	
Ceiling	1475	Rockwool	678	Rockwool	156
		EPS	670	EPS	155
		Cork	624	Cork	150
Roof	-	91		24	

Figure 30. Total embodied energy and carbon of the baseline scenario for different insulation materials (Rockwool, EPS, Cork)

Regarding the different insulation material, the results showed that cork allows a reduction of the embodied energy and carbon compared to EPS and rockwool in all structural element where insulation was required. However, these differences can be considered limited related to the overall new embodied energy and carbon, mainly due to low amount of insulation material required compared to the main building structures (i.e., bricks) and to the similar values of the thermophysical properties and embodied energy/carbon of the different materials (see Table 12). This is confirmed by observing Figure 30 where the total embodied energy and carbon resulting from the demolition, treatment and disposal of the old building and its reconstruction by using new material one can be estimated is illustrated. Figure 30 and 31 shows the results of the analysis on the embodied energy and carbon associated with the existing materials of the case study in case of low and high material recovery rates

respectively, based on the current structure conditions. For each scenario, the figures illustrate the share of the structural elements already present onsite which are conserved (i.e., reused), the share of the materials recycled after demolishing the remaining structures and the share of the material disposed in landfills. While the recycling process is assumed to be carried out onsite, the share of disposed material also includes the embodied energy and carbon associated with material processing, transportation and final disposal. As expected, the LR scenario shows low percentages of materials reused and recycled, with percentages below 25% and 35% of the embodied energy and carbon recovered. However, the HR scenario demonstrates that high shares of embodied energy and carbon can be recovered, depending on the element characteristics and conservation status, with percentages up to 65% and 75% respectively.

Both Figure 30 and Figure 31 illustrate that, in this specific case study, most of material which can be recovered and/or recycled are related to vertical walls (external and internal), while a limited recovery rate can be obtained by basements/floors and roof

structures, due to their poor conservation status. This is particularly true for roof elements, since most of the structures collapsed or are in a highly degraded status, which makes their reusability unfeasible for safety reason

Figure 31. Share of embodied energy and carbon related to the materials reused (conserved structural elements), recycled and disposed in landfill for the Low Recovery (LR) scenario

Figure 32. Share of embodied energy and carbon related to the materials reused (conserved structural elements), recycled and disposed in landfill for the High Recovery (HR) scenario.

Figure 33 shows the recovered embodied energy and carbon obtained in the two analysed scenarios for the three different insulation materials adopted. Firstly, it can be noted that the recovery indexes values in the range 7.5%-8.9% and 17%-17.8% for the LR and HR scenarios respectively were obtained for the specific case study under analysis. For both scenarios, the use of cork as insulation material allows to reduce the total embodied energy and carbon, and consequently increasing the recovery indexes, resulting from the refurbishment of the building complex

under analysis, thanks to its lower specific embodied content (Table 12). On the other hand, rockwool shows the lowest recovery index for both scenarios. However, low variations in terms of energy carbon recovery indexes can be spotted as function of the insulation material used. As explained previously, this is related to the relative limited impact of the insulation quantities compared to the overall material requirements for the entire building refurbishment.

Figure 33. Recovered embodied energy and carbon indexes for different insulation materials (rockwool, EPS, cork) in case of (a) low-recovery (LR) and (b) high-recovery (HR) scenarios

Conclusion and Recommendations

Recycling in the building construction sector specifically involves the collection, processing, and reuse of materials from building construction and demolition sites and it represents a fundamental phase which can contribute significantly to the reduction of new material consumptions and related energy and carbon costs. Generally, the potential for reusing a large amount of abandoned material in the building process requires a

large amount of abandoned material in the building process requires a comprehensive life-cycle approach that encompasses everything from the selection of the construction site to the selection of building materials and design elements, from the construction to its operating life and decommissioning.

In this context, the present case study analysed the potential renovation of a former urban industrial building block, named "Ex Concerie Costa", inserted in the urban context of the city close to the city centre of Sassari, Sardinia (Italy). The main complex, which consists of a 3-floor building with about 1543 m² per floor, was built starting from 1859 and expanded over several decades and eventually abandoned. Currently, the building complex is in an advanced state of decay, although its location close to the city and to the main roads and railway makes it an ideal location for a variety of new

uses, both commercial and industrial. The analysis was carried out in terms of embodied energy and embodied carbon related to the existing materials on-site and the assessment of their potential recovery for the building complex refurbishment. The refurbishment of the entire complex was assumed to be carried out by maintaining the same building complex layout and characteristics.

A preliminary analysis was performed on the building elements, which showed that a relatively large amount of available material, and therefore embodied energy and carbon, is available onsite (Table 5). Then, two different scenarios were defined based on the estimated amount of structural element reuse and material recycling potential (i.e., low-recovery and high-recovery scenarios). The embodied energy and carbon estimation - related to demolition, material transportation and landfill disposal costs - were also considered.

The results showed that a large potential of material recovery (and consequently embodied energy and carbon contents) is present, ranging from 25%-35% for the low-recovery scenario to 65%-75% for the high-recovery scenario, with the highest share for vertical external and internal walls. Generally, the dismantling scenario is the most preferable, but it depends on the state of conservation of the pre-existing building materials.

Furthermore, the analysis was extended to investigate the influence of using different insulation materials (i.e., rockwool, EPS and cork) on the embodied energy and carbon recovery indexes for the specific building complex. The results showed that cork allows for a reduction in the total embodied energy and carbon, and consequently increases the recovery indexes. Notwithstanding, low variations in terms of energy carbon recovery indexes can

be spotted as function of the insulation material used, due to the relative limited impact of the insulation quantities compared to the overall material requirements for the entire building refurbishment.

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